

Black Bodies as Baroque Decorations: Africans and Aristocratic Self-Representation in Polish-Lithuanian Portraiture

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Abstract

This working paper examines a group of eighteenth-century portraits from the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth that depict elite women accompanied by Black attendants. It asks how such figures entered aristocratic self-representation in a society without overseas colonies, but entangled in wider European aristocratic networks, visual culture and colonial imagination. Focusing mainly on portraits of Tekla Róża Radziwiłł and Magdalena Radziwiłł née Czapska, the paper reads Black attendants not as straightforward portraits of identifiable individuals, but as racialised visual tropes used to highlight particular messages of the artwork. At the same time, the paper does not treat these images as merely decorative. By placing them alongside archival evidence for African presence at Radziwiłł courts, including the purchase and training of African children for courtly performance, it suggests that painted fantasy and lived dependency were closely connected. The paper argues that Polish-Lithuanian magnates could participate in what may be called coloniality without colonies: not through direct overseas rule, but through the appropriation, display and aestheticisation of real racialised bodies and their images within Baroque elite culture.

Keywords: African history; Black history; Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth; Baroque portraiture; Radziwiłł family; aristocratic self-representation; racialisation; slavery; dependency; early modern Europe

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Introduction

As a historian, not an art historian, I came to visual sources almost by necessity. The written evidence for Black history in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth is scarce, uneven and often frustratingly silent or even silenced. And yet, a small number of visual representations are cultural evidence in their own right. They can tell us something about the place of Black bodies in elite imagination.

The question that first brought me to this material was simple, but not easy to answer. Why did Polish-Lithuanian magnates bring captured Africans so far from the main routes of the Atlantic slave trade? In the Commonwealth, bonded labour was certainly not lacking. This means that the motivation was unlikely to be primarily economic. As in many other European contexts, it was first of all cultural. I would suggest that it was the very essence of the Baroque, with its fascination with the exotic and the strange, and with its tendency to turn them into symbolic and allegorical forms, that facilitated both the use of Black figures and the traffic in real Africans.

Baroque culture was shaped, to a considerable degree, by encounters with non-European others: with the exciting and threatening “Orient”, but also with the newly discovered *terrae incognitae* of the Atlantic world and the global South. These encounters could produce exchange, curiosity, imitation and even admiration. At the same time, they also opened the way to cultural colonisation: the extraction, appropriation and repurposing of objects, images, meanings and even bodies within European culture.

At first sight, this may seem less relevant to societies situated far from the colonial metropolises. The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth did not possess overseas colonies and did not build a maritime empire, but this does not mean that it was outside the colonial world-system.¹ Polish-Lithuanian elites could act, in a sense, as colonialists without colonies. They did not rule overseas territories directly, but they were integrated into wider European and global circulation of goods, fashions, images and fantasies. In some elite milieus, this symbolic consumption of coloniality left visible traces.

Black attendants in elite portraiture

I want to test this framework through a small but remarkable group of portraits: Baroque images of elite women accompanied by Black attendants. This pictorial type had a long European history. It can be traced back at least to Titian’s portrait of Laura Dianti (see Figure 1 in Appendix), painted in the 1520s. During the following almost three centuries, roughly up to the end of the eighteenth century, similar portraits appeared in different parts of Europe. They were never among the most common formats of elite portraiture, but the surviving material is still considerable. Numerous examples show royalty, nobles and, in some cases, wealthy commoners, often women, placed beside Black attendants.²

¹ See: Marian Małowist, *Western Europe, Eastern Europe and World Development, 13th–18th Centuries*, ed. Jean Batou and Henryk Szlajfer (Leiden: Brill, 2010); Bolaji Balogun, *Race and the Colour-Line: The Boundaries of Europeanness in Poland* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2024).

² Kate Lowe, “The Lives of African Slaves and People of African Descent in Renaissance Europe,” in *Revealing the African Presence in Renaissance Europe*, ed. Joaneath Spicer (Baltimore: Walters Art Museum, 2012), 17–19. David Bindman, “Subjectivity and Slavery in Portraiture: From Courtly to Commercial

A few such portraits also survive from the aristocratic culture of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Their presence allows us to ask how Polish-Lithuanian elites adopted and adapted visual languages already recognisable in wider Europe.

If well-known royal portraits are left aside, and the focus is placed only on aristocratic representations, I have so far been able to identify four portraits from the Commonwealth that include Black attendants (Figures 2–5). All of them depict women. In this paper, I concentrate on two portraits that were produced for, and used most directly within, a Polish-Lithuanian context (Figures 4–5). Both portray women connected to the powerful Radziwiłł family.

The Radziwiłłs belonged to one of the most influential magnate families of the Commonwealth. Their rise began in the sixteenth century, from relatively modest Lithuanian *boyar* origins, and was symbolically confirmed in 1547, when they received the title of Princes of the Holy Roman Empire. In the early modern period, they held some of the highest state offices, accumulated enormous landed wealth and built marriage alliances with royal and princely houses across Europe. It is therefore hardly surprising that by the eighteenth century they had ambitions for the throne, or at least sought to act as the Commonwealth’s “uncrowned kings”.³

Evidence of African presence in Radziwiłł residences can be traced at least to the second half of the sixteenth century.⁴ However, Black people seem to enter the Radziwiłłs’ visual self-representation only much later, in the early eighteenth century. The gap between their earlier archival presence and their later appearance in portraits and other visual material is worth noticing. It suggests that, over time, Black figures acquired new meanings and functions, manifested among other things in these new forms of display.

The portraits discussed here were created during the rule of the Saxon Wettin dynasty in the Commonwealth: Augustus II, followed by his son Augustus III. The court of Augustus II moved regularly between Dresden and Warsaw, strengthening transregional courtly ties between the Commonwealth and the German-speaking world. Augustus II was known not only for his reputation as a prolific lover but also for his taste for exoticism. He promoted Ottoman-inspired fashions, commissioned Turkish-style military bands and surrounded himself with various manifestations of the “exotic”.⁵ It is also significant that he, his queen, his son, and even his lovers were portrayed in several paintings with Black attendants.⁶

Tekla Róża Radziwiłł and her “slave of love”

This Saxon courtly culture formed the immediate visual background for the first portrait discussed here – the portrait of Tekla Róża Radziwiłł with a Black attendant (Figure 4). It is usually dated, rather broadly, to the 1720s. Tekla Róża was the daughter of Anna Katarzyna Radziwiłł, an

Societies,” in *Slave Portraiture in the Atlantic World*, ed. Agnes Lugo-Ortiz and Angela Rosenthal (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2013), 71.

³ Tadeusz Bernatowicz, *Mitra i buława: królewskie ambicje książąt w sztuce Rzeczypospolitej szlacheckiej (1697–1763)* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2011), 79–82, 150–151.

⁴ Raimonda Ragauskienė, Lietuvos Didžiosios Kunigaikštystės kancleris Mikalojus Radvila Rudasis (Vilnius: Seimo leidykla „Valstybės žinios“, 2002), 234.

⁵ Haydn Williams, *Turquerie: An Eighteenth-Century European Fantasy* (London: Thames & Hudson, 2014), 66–74.

⁶ Rebekka von Mallinckrodt, “Iconography and the Law: Slaves at the Dresden Court,” in *The European Experience in Slavery, 1650–1850*, ed. Rebekka von Mallinckrodt (Berlin and Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2024), 154–157.

ambitious and politically active widow. She was well educated and served her mother as librarian and secretary. At the same time, she managed to escape her mother's control. Against Anna Katarzyna's matrimonial plans, Tekla Róża initiated a relationship with Jakob Heinrich von Flemming, a powerful Saxon statesman and field marshal at the court of Augustus II, twenty-seven years her senior. They married in 1725, as it turned out, only three years before Flemming's death.⁷ It is not entirely clear whether the portrait was commissioned before or after the marriage, although I would cautiously assume that it was more likely painted soon after it.⁸ After the marriage, Tekla Róża got involved in the life of the royal court, travelling between Poland and Saxony.⁹

The work was painted by Louis de Silvestre, a French-born artist who served as court painter to Augustus II. Silvestre produced many high-status portraits of the king, his family and members of his court.¹⁰ This makes comparison especially useful. When we place the Black attendant in Tekla Róża's portrait beside the attendants in portraits of Augustus II and his wife,¹¹ the similarities are difficult to miss. The costumes appear almost identical, or at least based on a shared model. Africanness is emphasised, even exaggerated, through very dark skin, stylised features, and dramatic contrast with the pale body of the noble sitter.

Two details are especially remarkable. The first is the metal collar worn by the Black figures. It is a sign of enslavement, but it is also presented as if it were a precious accessory, made of valuable metal. The collar highlights the attendant's enslaved status, while also aestheticising it. Although it was probably rarely part of actual attire, the metal collar became a regular attribute of servitude in art.¹²

The second element, which complements but also changes the meaning of the collar, is the earring. This detail was a common early modern emblem, referring to an Old Testament tradition in which the ear of a slave could be marked if he refused freedom and chose to remain with his master.¹³ Thus, the combination of collar and earring could transform the Black attendant into a stylised allegorical figure: not necessarily a literal servant, but a "slave of love", imagined as remaining in devoted service through affection, loyalty, or desire.¹⁴ The parrot in the portrait adds another layer, since it could carry meanings of love and obedience, both of which fit the painting's broader

⁷ Anna Penkała-Jastrzębska, "To Marry a Foreigner ...": *Migrations and the Marriage Policy of the Nobility of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth*, trans. Mariola Dyl-Wąsik, Series of the Friedrich Christian Lesser Foundation 43 (Mühlhausen/Thür.: Friedrich-Christian-Lesser-Stiftung; Nordhausen: Verlag Steffen Iffland, 2021), 186-187.

⁸ I am grateful to Professor Lorenzo Pericolo, who, during the discussion following my conference presentation, identified the flowers depicted in the portrait as orange blossoms, a symbol of marriage, thereby suggesting a possible clue to the portrait's dating.

⁹ Penkała-Jastrzębska, "To Marry a Foreigner ...", 196-197.

¹⁰ Krystyna Gutowska-Dudek, *Między światem mitów i legend a współczesnością. Louis de Silvestre – nadworny malarz królów Polski z dynastii Wettynów* (Warszawa: Muzeum Pałacu Króla Jana III w Wilanowie, 2015), 31-35.

¹¹ Mallinckrodt, "Iconography and the Law," figs. 7.1-7.2, 152, 155.

¹² Elizabeth McGrath, "Caryatids, Page Boys, and African Fetters: Themes of African Slavery in European Art," in *The Slave in European Art: From Renaissance Trophy to Abolitionist Emblem*, ed. Elizabeth McGrath and Jean Michel Massing, Warburg Institute Colloquia 20 (London and Turin: The Warburg Institute and Nino Aragno Editore, 2012), 14-16.

¹³ McGrath, "Caryatids, Page Boys, and African Fetters," 17.

¹⁴ Noémie Ndiaye, *Scripts of Blackness: Early Modern Performance Culture and the Making of Race* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2022), 93.

message.¹⁵ The painting presents the princess as a fair beauty, worthy of the marvellous treasures of the world and of devoted, almost slavish love.

At almost the same moment, we also have archival evidence for a real Black attendant in the Radziwiłł household, in the service of Anna Katarzyna Radziwiłł, Tekla Róża's mother. The financial documentation around 1740 briefly mentions a Black woman.¹⁶ This later reference raises a different question: could the presence of a real Black attendant be understood as a kind of real-life enactment of the same cultural motif? In other words, did the visual fashion for Black attendants help to create a desire for their actual presence at court?

Magdalena Radziwiłł and the embodiment of obedience

A similar reading, I would argue, can be applied to the second portrait (Figure 5). It confirms many of the observations made above, but the emphasis is slightly different. Here, the image moves away from the romantic allegory of service and comes closer to a more political language of power and obedience.

The portrait depicts Magdalena Radziwiłł, born into the Czapski family, a prominent noble house from Royal Prussia. This was a region of the Polish Crown with a strong German-speaking presence and cultural influence. Magdalena herself grew up in cosmopolitan Gdańsk. She later became the second wife of Hieronim Florian Radziwiłł, who was one of the most extravagant and controversial figures in the history of the Radziwiłł family.

Like many magnates, Hieronim Florian entertained royal ambitions. He believed in prophecies about his future election to the throne. In practice, however, he never built a serious political career within the Commonwealth. Instead, he fashioned himself as a kind of independent ruler on his estates in Biała Podlaska and Słuck. Within his own domains, he imitated German princely styles of rule and maintained a private army organised in a Prussian manner. His enormous wealth made such self-fashioning possible, but he also had a notorious reputation for cruelty.¹⁷

The Czapski family effectively pushed Magdalena into a secret engagement and marriage with Hieronim in 1745, even before the legal matters around his previous divorce had been fully resolved. However, this marriage also did not last long. Magdalena did not produce an heir and suffered from her husband's notorious temper. After five years, she followed the example of Hieronim's first wife and fled from her cruel husband.¹⁸

Around 1745, not long after their wedding, the couple commissioned a pair of matching portraits: one showing Magdalena and the other Hieronim Florian. The portraits were intended as a set and were installed in the newly renovated main hall of the Biała Palace.¹⁹ They were painted by

¹⁵ Sigrid Dittrich and Lothar Dittrich, *Lexikon der Tiersymbole: Tiere als Sinnbilder in der Malerei des 14.–17. Jahrhunderts* (Petersberg: Michael Imhof Verlag, 2004), 322–32

¹⁶ Anna Penkała-Jastrzębska, "Służba na kobiecym dworze magnackim," in *Dwór kobiety w Rzeczypospolitej XVII i XVIII wieku*, ed. Bożena Popiołek, Anna Penkała-Jastrzębska, and Katarzyna Pyzel (Kraków: Libron, 2021), 168–69.

¹⁷ Hanna Dymnicka-Wołoszyńska, "Radziwiłł Hieronim Florian h. Trąby," in *Polski słownik biograficzny*, vol. 30/1, issue 124, *Radwan–Radziwiłł Jan* (Wrocław, Warszawa, Kraków, Gdańsk, and Łódź: Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich; Wydawnictwo Polskiej Akademii Nauk, 1987), 185–88.

¹⁸ Paweł Gad, "„Najukochońszy tyran” — Hieronim Florian Radziwiłł w listach drugiej żony Magdaleny z Czapskich," *Wiek Stary i Nowy* 8, no. 13 (2015): 69–70, 85.

¹⁹ Bernatowicz, *Mitra i bulawa*, 300.

Jakob Wessel, one of the leading Gdańsk artists of the mid-eighteenth century, who had trained in Berlin in the circle of Antoine Pesne.²⁰ Unlike Louis de Silvestre, or Antoine Pesne, Wessel does not seem, at least on the basis of the material known to me, to have produced other portraits featuring Black attendants.²¹ This may suggest that the inclusion of such a figure was not simply part of his usual pictorial repertoire, but responded to a specific expectation of the commissioner.

In the portrait, Magdalena is depicted as a proud princess. Her posture is straight and authoritative. Her status is underlined by the princely cape with sable, a typical sign of princely rank in Polish-Lithuanian portraiture.²² The Black page beside her offers her flowers and gazes upwards with theatrical admiration. He bears a striking resemblance to the figure in Tekla Róża's portrait, painted almost two decades earlier. The same visual vocabulary appears again: facial features conventionally associated with Africanness in European portraiture, very dark skin, similar costume details, the metal slave collar, and the manumission earring. It is tempting to ask whether he was copied, directly or indirectly, from the earlier portrait of Hieronim Florian's sister.

Together with the princely cape, the Black attendant symbolises here not so much a romantic allegory of love as an allegory of absolute obedience. This reading fits Hieronim Florian's personality rather well. He disliked the demonstrative equality of the Polish-Lithuanian nobility and was notorious for harsh punishments imposed on his subjects, even for minor disobedience.²³ His monarchical ambitions may help explain why this type of portrait, uncommon among Polish-Lithuanian aristocrats but familiar in German court traditions, appeared in his household and what message it was meant to convey.

From Painted Fantasy to Lived Presence: Africans at Radziwiłł's Court

Hieronim Florian Radziwiłł is also connected to one of the most remarkable and still little-studied episodes in the Black history of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. One may wonder whether his inspiration for this initiative came, at least partly, from the daily presence of the portrait of Magdalena Czapska and her Black attendant, displayed prominently in the great hall of Biała Palace.

The idea of employing and displaying real African servants seems to have captured Hieronim Florian's imagination. Shortly after the wedding and the commissioning of Magdalena's portrait, in 1748, a princely official brought a Black boy from Vienna to Radziwiłł's court. He was described by Hieronim in his diary as a Congolese prince Rabinda, captured by the French.²⁴ Then, in 1752, after Magdalena had already escaped from the marriage, another representative of Radziwiłł purchased a

²⁰ Anna Mosingiewicz, "Efigies ante omnia: Malarstwo portretowe w Gdańsku XVIII wieku," in *Portret ponad wszystko: Jacob Wessel i jego wiek. Sztuka gdańska XVIII wieku*, ed. Anna Mosingiewicz and Dariusz Kaczor, exhibition catalogue, Muzeum Narodowe w Gdańsku, 15 December 2005–26 February 2006 (Gdańsk: Muzeum Narodowe w Gdańsku, 2005), 39–40.

²¹ Catalogue of Wessel's portraits: *Portret ponad wszystko: Jacob Wessel i jego wiek. Sztuka gdańska XVIII wieku*, ed. Anna Mosingiewicz and Dariusz Kaczor, exhibition catalogue, Muzeum Narodowe w Gdańsku, 15 December 2005–26 February 2006 (Gdańsk: Muzeum Narodowe w Gdańsku, 2005), 52–77.

²² Bernatowicz, *Mitra i bulawa*, 64.

²³ Dymnicka-Wołoszyńska, "Radziwiłł Hieronim Florian," 186–187.

²⁴ Hieronim Florian Radziwiłł, *Hieronima Floriana Radziwiłła diariusze i pisma różne*, ed. Maria Strycharska-Brzezina (Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Energeia, 1998), 84.

group of twelve African children in London.²⁵ They were transferred to Biała and then to Słuck, another Radziwiłł residence. There, under the direction of an Italian theatre director in princely service, the children were trained as ballet dancers for participation in the court theatre. The results were mixed: only three of the African youths reportedly succeeded in becoming performers in the court troupe and appeared in staged productions. However, after the deaths of Hieronim Florian and especially of his brother Michał Kazimierz Radziwiłł Rybeńko, the court theatre entered a period of decline.²⁶ The remaining youths, if they survived the harsh climate and disease, remained in the roles of attendants or servants and were assigned to different tasks, including labour in the Persian sash manufactory.²⁷

This episode shows quite clearly how closely imagination and exploitation could be connected. The symbolic use of Blackness in portraiture was not merely decorative. It belonged to a broader elite fantasy of possessing and displaying Black bodies as living Baroque allegories, and as living proof of a magnate's global reach. However, once the master's fantasy faded, they could be turned into ordinary servants or labourers, especially vulnerable and dependent.

Conclusion

What, then, can a researcher of Black history in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth take from these portraits? First of all, the Black figures shown in this type of image were probably not portraits of real individuals, or at least not in any straightforward sense. They appear rather as idealised and abstracted “Moors”, created not to document reality but to work as visual tropes in elite Baroque self-fashioning. Their clothing, jewellery and accessories, including silver slave collars and earrings associated with manumission, were not necessarily based on what actual servants at court wore. They belonged instead to a symbolic visual vocabulary circulating through European aristocratic culture.

For this reason, portraits such as those of Tekla Róża and Magdalena Radziwiłł with Black attendants offer only limited biographical insight into the lives of Black people in the aristocratic and royal courts of the Commonwealth. However, these depictions provide valuable insight into elite imagination: how Blackness was imagined, visualised and employed. They suggest that the presence of Black figures was not primarily about labour, but about display, status, obedience, possession and the ability to turn the exotic into Baroque allegory. The later case of Hieronim Florian Radziwiłł's African servants shows that this imagination could also have material consequences. Painted Black attendants and real African dependants belonged to the same aristocratic culture of display, even if the archival traces of individual lives remain fragmentary.

To read such material properly, we need a method that is not only archival, but also iconographic, symbolic and decolonial. Such a method should pay attention both to what is shown and to what is carefully hidden in the making of noble identity on the eastern fringes of early modern Europe.

²⁵ Janusz Tazbir, *Rzeczpospolita i świat* (Wrocław: Zakład Narodowy im. Ossolińskich, 1971), 89.

²⁶ Irena Bieńkowska, *Muzyka na dworze księcia Hieronima Floriana Radziwiłła* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2013), 260-265.

²⁷ D. V. Liseichikov and E. S. Glinskii, *Madzharskie: armianskii rod v istorii Belarusi* [Маджарские: армянский род в истории Беларуси] (Yerevan and Minsk: Fond “ANIV” and NIAB, 2023), 184.

This small case also suggests how a European hinterland, a society of “colonialists without colonies”, was entangled in broader European colonial expansion. Baroque culture was one of the important media of this entanglement. It commodified, appropriated and reproduced subjugated images, objects and people, even in places that did not possess colonies of their own.

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Appendix: Figures

Figure 1. Titian, *Portrait of Laura Dianti*, c. 1520–1525, oil on canvas, Heinz Kisters Collection, Kreuzlingen. Digital image from Wikimedia Commons, Public Domain Mark 1.0. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tizian_058.jpg (accessed 26 June 2026).

Figure 2. *Joanna Maria de Béthune Jabłonowska*, c. 1690–1700, oil on canvas. Unknown artist. Jagiellonian University Museum, Kraków, inv. no. 2593. Public-domain digital reproduction via Wikimedia Commons:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Portret_Joanny_z_B%C3%A9thun%C3%B3w_Jab%C5%82onowskiej.jpg (accessed 26 June 2026).

Figure 3. *Portrait of Maria Carolina de Bouillon (Maria Karolina Sobieska)*, c. 1730. Oil on canvas. Unknown artist. Museum of King Jan III's Palace at Wilanów. Wikimedia Commons, Public Domain Mark 1.0:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Portrait_of_Maria_Carolina_de_Bouillon -
_Google_Art_Project.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Portrait_of_Maria_Carolina_de_Bouillon_-_Google_Art_Project.jpg). (accessed 26 June 2026).

Figure 4. *Tekla Róża Radziwiłł*, 1720s, Louis de Silvestre, oil on canvas, National Art Museum of the Republic of Belarus, Minsk. Digital image via Wikimedia Commons (Public Domain Mark 1.0). Available at: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tekl%C4%97_Ro%C5%BE%C4%97_Radvilait%C4%97.jpg (accessed 26 June 2026).

Figure 5. *Portrait of Magdalena Radziwiłł née Czapska*, 1746. Oil on canvas, by Jacob Wessel. National Museum in Warsaw (inv. MP 2437). Digital image via Wikimedia Commons, Public Domain Mark 1.0. Available at: [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Jakub_Wessel_-_Portrait_of_Magdalena_Radziwi%C5%82%C5%82_n%C3%A9_Czapska_\(%5E%E2%80%9363\)_-MP_2437_-_National_Museum_in_Warsaw.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Jakub_Wessel_-_Portrait_of_Magdalena_Radziwi%C5%82%C5%82_n%C3%A9_Czapska_(%5E%E2%80%9363)_-MP_2437_-_National_Museum_in_Warsaw.jpg) (accessed 26 June 2026).